

Zeolite clinoptilolite/ZnFe₂O₄/NiWO₄ nanocomposite: preparation and its application for the removal of chemical nerve agent simulant dimethyl 4-nitrophenyl phosphate (DMNP)

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Abstract

The present study focuses on the activity of novel clinoptilolite/ZnFe₂O₄/NiWO₄ nanocomposite catalyst for the removal of chemical nerve agent simulant dimethyl 4-nitrophenyl phosphate (DMNP) for the first time. The experiments were all implemented by isopropanol and n-heptane solvents and subsequently monitored by using ³¹P NMR and UV-Vis analyses. The as-prepared nanocomposite was well identified by FE-SEM, EDAX, VSM, FTIR, and XRD. The ³¹P NMR and UV-Vis outcomes indicated that DMNP molecule was completely removed over the clinoptilolite/ZnFe₂O₄/NiWO₄ nanocomposite in n-heptane solvent after contact time of 5 min at room temperature. It seems that non-polar solvent helps the material transfer to the available active sites of in the nanocomposite surface without blocking them. Lastly, p-nitrophenole (p-NP) and dimethyl phosphoric acid (DMPA) as the hydrolysis products of DMNP were identified, respectively. This research provides a viable solution for using based-zeolite nanocomposite for the removal of highly toxic organophosphorus agents.

Keywords: clinoptilolite/ZnFe₂O₄/NiWO₄, zeolite, nanocomposite, DMNP, nerve agent simulant, removal, hydrolysis.